

Chromatographic separation of amino acids on paper impregnated with zirconium(IV) sulfosalicylate

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Manuscript received 11 April 2002, revised 3 March 2003, accepted 4 March 2003

Zirconium(IV) sulfosalicylate impregnated paper has been utilized for chromatographic studies of amino acids. hR_f values of 24 amino acids have been studied in five eluting systems. Some analytically important binary and ternary separations of amino acids have been achieved.

Laskar *et al.*¹ have reported a modified spray reagent for identification of amino acids. Sharma *et al.*² studied the effect of mobile phase composition and pH on chromatographic behaviour of amino acids. Zirconium(IV) sulfosalicylate has been utilized for separation of metal ions³.

This paper reports the results of chromatographic studies of 24 amino acids on zirconium(IV) impregnated paper. The influence of eluting solvents on chromatographic behaviour has been investigated. On the basis of difference in hR_f ($100 \times R_f$) values the mixtures of amino acids have been separated successfully.

Results and discussion

In order to investigate the influence of developing solvents the chromatographic studies were carried out in five different electrolytes. The hR_f values determined for 24 amino acids are presented in Table 1. Amino acids show differential rate of migration (hR_f) on zirconium(IV) sulfosalicylate impregnated paper. The chromatographic behaviour seems to depend upon the nature of the exchanger as well as eluting reagents.

The chromatographic studies reveal that basic amino acids do not migrate ($hR_f = 0$) and acidic and neutral amino acids show only little migration ($hR_f = 4-17$) in methanol : butanol system (1 : 1). Each amino acid has a hydrocarbon chain and at least two hydrophilic groups (one amino and one carboxylic group). The retention of amino acid on impregnated paper may be explained on the basis of hydrogen bonding between $-NH_2$ group of amino acid and $-OH$ group present in zirconium(IV) sulfosalicylate³. Pires and Roseria have also suggested such possibility of hydrogen bonding between aromatic amines and silica gel G⁴. It is cationic at lower pH, isoelectric near an intermediate (neutral) and anionic at higher pH. These transformations are represented by the following equilibria :

Table 1. hR_f values of amino acids on zirconium sulfosalicylate impregnated paper

No.	Amino acids	S ₁	S ₂	S ₃	S ₄	S ₅
<i>Neutral amino acids :</i>						
N ₁	Glycine	05	58	23	24	35
N ₂	L-Hydroxyproline	13	35	30	31	45
N ₃	DL-Alanine	07	27	19	10	43
N ₄	DL-Sarime	06	04	19	13	29
N ₅	L-Proline	09	18	26	33	54
N ₆	DL-Valine	12	22	36	59	74
N ₇	DL-Threonine	17	25	38	31	60
N ₈	L-Leusine	13	60	61	60	75
N ₉	DL-Iso-leucine	17	50	68	31	71
N ₁₀	GL-Methionine	15	03	47	41	52
N ₁₁	L-Tyrosine	04	42	29	44	31
N ₁₂	DL-β-Phenyl alanine	08	45	62	74	80
N ₁₃	DL-Tryptophan	06	19	63	36	64
N ₁₄	DL-3,4-Dihydroxyphenylalanine	04	18	19	34	35
N ₁₅	L-Cysteine	15	36	32	57	11
N ₁₆	DL-2-Amino-n-butyric acid	07	25	28	37	39
N ₁₇	L-Cysteine.HCl	08	20	21	24	31
N ₁₈	DL-Nor leucine	09	61	40	60	76
<i>Acidic amino acids :</i>						
A ₁	DL-Aspartic acid	04	15	14	15	21
A ₂	L-Glutamic acid	05	24	51	32	58
<i>Basic amino acids :</i>						
B ₁	L-Lysine.HCl	00	05	15	26	33
B ₂	DL-Ornithine.HCl	00	13	17	19	44
B ₃	L-Histidine.HCl	00	32	46	53	40
B ₄	L-Arginine.HCl	00	09	27	14	29

S₁ = Methanol : n-butanol (1 : 1), S₂ = n-butanol : acetic acid : water (4 : 1 : 1), S₃ = n-butanol : ethyl acetate : acetic acid : water (4 : 2 : 1 : 3), S₄ = n-butanol : ethyl acetate : acetic acid : water (4 : 3 : 2 : 1), S₅ = n-butanol : acetic acid : water (4 : 3 : 2 : 1).

Higher hR_f values in acidic systems may be due to greater elution of cationic form of amino acids by the competing H^+ ions because zirconium(IV) sulfosalicylate behaves as a cation exchanger³.

Detection : The spots were detected by spraying with ninhydrin solution (2% w/v in ethanol) and heating the paper strips at $70 \pm 5^\circ$.

Table 2. Separation of amino acids on zirconium sulfosalicylate impregnated papers

Solvent systems	Separations achieved
<i>n</i> -Butanol : acetone : acetic acid : water (4 : 3 : 2 : 1)	N ₄ (29)–N ₈ (73) N ₁₁ (30)–N ₈ (74) N ₁₄ (35)–N ₁₂ (80) N ₁₇ (30)–N ₁₈ (75) B ₃ (40)–N ₁₈ (75) A ₁ (22)–N ₈ (74) A ₁ (20)–A ₂ (57) N ₄ (28)–N ₁₃ (64) N ₁ (35)–N ₆ (72) N ₁₅ (10)–N ₁₁ (30)–N ₈ (75) N ₁₅ (10)–N ₁₆ (40)–N ₁₂ (80) N ₄ (28)–N ₇ (60)–N ₁₂ (80) N ₁ (20)–B ₂ (44)–N ₁₂ (80)
<i>n</i> -Butanol : acetic acid : water (4 : 1 : 1)	N ₂ (36)–N ₈ (60) N ₇ (25)–N ₉ (49) N ₂ (35)–N ₁₈ (60) B ₄ (8)–B ₃ (32) B ₁ (5)–B ₃ (32) A ₂ (23)–N ₁₂ (45) N ₄ (4)–N ₁₅ (36)–N ₈ (60) B ₄ (10)–N ₂ (35)–N ₈ (60)
<i>n</i> -Butanol : ethyl acetate : acetic acid : water (4 : 2 : 1 : 3)	N ₇ (37)–N ₈ (60) N ₁₁ (28)–N ₁₃ (64) N ₁₁ (28)–N ₁₂ (61) B ₂ (17)–B ₃ (46) B ₁ (14)–N ₁₁ (30)–N ₈ (60) B ₂ (18)–N ₆ (36)–N ₉ (66) A ₁ (12)–N ₁₁ (28)–N ₁₃ (62) N ₁₄ (20)–N ₁₀ (46)–N ₉ (67)

Chromatography : On the basis of difference in hR_f values (Table 1), the separations of amino acids were tried. The binary and ternary separations achieved experimentally are summarized in Table 2. The analytical potentiality of zirconium(IV) sulfosalicylate impregnated paper is demonstrated by achieving quantitative separations of N₂–N₈, B₄–B₃ and A₂–N₁₂ in *n*-butanol : acetic acid : water (4 : 1 : 1) system. These amino acids (2–10 μg) could be separated quantitatively in their synthetic mixtures.

Experimental

Zirconium(IV) dichloride oxide octahydrate (C.D.H., India), amino acids (B.D.H., England) and sulfosalicylic acid (LOBA, India) were used. All other reagents were of analytical grade. 0.1% solutions (w/v) of amino acids were prepared in double distilled water. A 2% solution of ninhydrin (Fluka, Switzerland) in ethanol was used.

Preparation of ion exchanger papers : Whatman no. 1 paper strips (15 × 3 cm) were dipped in 0.1 M zirconium dichloride oxide octahydrate solution for 15–20 s and then dried at room temperature. These strips were then dipped in 0.1 M sulfosalicylic acid solution for 40–50 s. The excess of reagent was allowed to drain off and the strips were dried at room temperature over the filter paper sheets. These treated strips were washed with double distilled water to remove excess of the reagent. Finally, the strips were dried at room temperature and used for chromatography.

Procedure : Standard amino acid solutions were spotted on paper strips with the help of a fine glass capillary. The paper was conditioned for 15 min and then solvent was allowed to ascend 12 cm in every case using 20 × 5 cm glass jars. For quantitative studies micropipettes were used for spotting. The area of developed chromatogram was measured using transparent graph paper and counting millimeters to nearest half square using magnifying lens.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (B.S.) is grateful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for financial assistance.

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